

COMPARATIVE AFFIXES AND AFFIXOIDS

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Abstract. This article provides information about comparative relations and the means of expressing them. In particular, the expression of the comparison relation through affixes and affixoid means is highlighted on the example of the Uzbek language. For example, in the Uzbek language, there are seven morphemes and six auxiliaries that express the relation of comparison.

Key words: affixes, lexical units, morphological tools, syntactic units.

In every language, especially in Uzbek and English, there is a set of verbal tools that realize the comparative description of the objects (person, thing, sign, quantity, manner (state), action, event) whose relation of comparison is compared. they form a single system.

In each particular language, the relation (or concept) of comparison is expressed through the following verbalizers in different system languages:

1. Affixes.
2. Lexical units.
3. Morphological units.
4. Syntactic units:
 - sentences;
 - texts[2;71-73].

In this study, we will consider the expression of the comparison relation by affixes and affixoids. When the concept of comparison is expressed by morphemes, these morphemes are in the composition of the above-mentioned comparative, i.e., the compared image - word. The morphemes representing the concept of comparison are:

In Uzbek:

Through affixes:

- a) *-roq;*
- b) *-dan;*
- c) *-guncha;*
- d) *-ganda;*
- e) *-ga;*
- f) *-sa;*
- g) *-may.*

Auxiliary words:

- a) *ko'ra;*

- b) nisbatan;
- c) qaraganda;
- d) bo'lsa, esa;
- e) qadar;
- f) lekin.

In the Uzbek language, the affix *-roq* is the only suffix that expresses the meaning of degree. When comparing the sign of two objects, although it indicates the excess (strength) of the sign, it does not express the excess, but the sign's inferiority, and serves to make it smaller [1;414]. It is appropriate to evaluate it as a reduced level. The affix *-roq* is used with the following tools:

- a) through the words such as *sal, biroz*;
- *Dokaning tepasidan tilibdi, sal pastroq bo'lganida, hech narsa qilmaskan.*(Nuriddin Ismoilov "Iblis saltanati")
- b) through *-dan*;
Odamsot uchun sahovatdan yaxshiroq va azizroq yoqimli sifat yo'q.(Hamidjon Xomidiy "Mashriqzamin hikmat bo'stoni")
- c) through *-ga*;
...ilmi jihatida yuqoriga o'tkazilgan kishilarga yaqinroq kishilar taklif etiladi.
- d) through the words such as *Qaraganda, nisbatan* [3;23].
Ilgari yonidagilariga nisbatan hiyla ko'rimsiz, pastroq edi.

As you can see from the above examples, more than one means can be involved in the comparison relation. In this case, one of them is the main, and the others are auxiliary comparative tools. Another of the most used tools of comparison in Uzbek linguistics is the affix *dan*, which is used together with lexical and morphological tools.

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